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Research Article

**THE RELEVANCE OF CREATING INFORMATION AND
CONSULTING SERVICES IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR****Anna Ermakova¹, Olga Berezhnaya², Elena Berezhnaya², Tatyana Belozerskaya³,
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Article Received: December 2018**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

In this article, based on data from a survey of heads of farms, an assessment is made of the state of their information support and identifies problems in this area. The possibility of creating an information and consulting service for small forms of agricultural entrepreneurship based on the use of telecommunication technologies is being considered.

So, the task of providing farmers with the necessary information, knowledge and technology should be assigned to information and advisory services. At the same time, the task of the consulting services at the first stage of operation should be the dissemination of modern information technologies, the formation of motivation for the use of scientific achievements, and the provision of advice to farmers based on their current needs. Building a well-functioning information and consulting service will help spread innovative technologies, reduce losses from making wrong decisions, which will allow peasant (farmer) farms to function and develop successfully.

Key words: agriculture, peasant, consulting, information, technology.

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INTRODUCTION:

An important condition for the sustainable development of agrarian entrepreneurship is a modern response to changes in market conditions and the adoption of informed decisions based on continuous monitoring of the market environment. At the same time, in the conditions of the increasing flow of incoming information, there is a need for its accumulation, processing and transfer to consumers - farms.

During the years of agrarian reform, the farm enterprise sector has become an integral part of the mixed farming of Russia. There is a steady growth trend in agricultural products produced in the farming sector. Over the past 10 years, the volume of production in peasant (farmer) farms in the Stavropol Territory increased by 7.9 times and in 2010 amounted to 8.4 billion rubles, or 565.5 thousand rubles. in based on 1 farm and 8.6 thousand rubles. from 1 hectare, which is 32% higher than the level reached in the agricultural organizations of the region [4].

Effective management and development of farmer entrepreneurship largely depends on the level of information competence of its employees and requires the development, implementation and system maintenance of information technologies, comprehensive automation programs and optimization of all production processes, forecasting and planning financial and economic indicators of farms.

The task of providing farms with the necessary information should be entrusted to information and advisory services, which are the most effective in comparison with other infrastructure entities. The main directions of information and consulting activities are [5]: informational - providing agribusiness enterprises with technological, economic, legal, market information; innovation - assistance in the development of innovation, promotion of research and development results in production; educational - training for farmers, as well as specialists and managers who provide services to peasant (farmer) farms. At the same time, information and consulting services should use a variety of ways to convey information to entrepreneurs and various financing options for these services.

However, the existing information and consulting services in our country cannot fully serve peasant (farmer) farms as a source of the necessary information. A limiting factor that does not allow to fully realize the potential of existing information and consulting services is both the high cost of the

services they provide and the low solvency of peasant (farmer) farms, and the use of outdated consulting technologies [1].

An expert survey of 89 heads of peasant (farmer) farms showed that most of the respondents (57.8%) constantly feel a lack of information and most often search for it themselves. At the same time, 25% of respondents believe that "they do not always have the opportunity to search for it," and appeals to consulting services cover only 10% of the information needs. According to 19.6% of heads of farms, this leads to the use of "unverified information and inefficient technologies", holding back the development of the economy [2].

Modern information and consulting services (ICS) should be mobile, take into account the specifics of the work of farms and offer them convenient, understandable information services. At the same time, the role of ICS should not be limited only to the transfer of information to peasant (farmer) farms. The most important task of information and consulting services is to improve the skills of heads of peasant (farmer) farms in order to develop their motivation to create high-tech production.

The heads of farms also pay attention to this. Thus, when answering the question: "Which forms of obtaining new information do you consider the most effective?" 26.6% of respondents indicated that they need, first of all, professional development, and 19.1% - in the consultations of specialists. In their opinion, the list of services provided to farms should include questions on accounting and taxation (89% of the number of respondents), on new technologies (68% of respondents), on product sales (91% of respondents), and legal advice (62 % of respondents) [2].

Based on the aforementioned, there is now a need to create a special information consulting structure that meets the needs of peasant (farmer) farms. In the formation of the modern structure of the ICS, it is necessary to consider both the basic principles of their functioning (purposefulness, structuring, adaptability, comfort, continuity of development, etc.), as well as specific, maximally adapted to PFF requests [3]. Thus, the information and consulting service should have an open architecture, it is necessary to create a single information space between it and peasant (farmer) farms, the presence of feedback between the service and farms, research and forecasting the needs of peasant (farmer) farms for information services.

Information and consulting service can not stop only on a certain set of services in advance. With the development of science and improvement of the structure of knowledge about the effective management of agro-industrial production, the ICS services provided to users should be constantly expanded.

In our opinion, the task of the consulting services at the first stage of operation should be the dissemination of information on modern information technologies, the formation of motivation for the use of scientific advances, and the provision of advice to farmers based on their current needs.

It should be borne in mind that for some services, farmers are ready to pay their full cost, for others - only a part, and the third, in their opinion, should be provided to them for free. Thus, farmers are ready to pay for the full cost of the following services: accounting assistance (89% of respondents), tax advice (91% of respondents), information on the state of the markets (83% of respondents). For partial payment, in their opinion, the following types of services can be provided: technical advice (62% of respondents), legal advice (35% of respondents) [2]. The most important condition for building an information and consulting service for farmers is the use of modern computer technologies, the systematic updating of information resources, the replenishment of data banks, as well as the continuous improvement of the information and consulting system depending on their needs.

Existing client-server telecommunications technologies significantly reduce the cost of building ICS, help to unite all service users into a single information network, and also allow the farmer to receive feedback from scientific institutions, identify and develop scientific research with a greater practical orientation. This increases the role of information and consulting services in the selection and dissemination of innovative technologies.

We can single out another important role of the information and consulting service: the exchange of experience between related structures, farms and scientific institutions regardless of their location, which will reduce the likelihood of using erroneous techniques and activities in the process of providing information services to users. To ensure the continuity of standards in the transfer of information between related structures, information and advisory services should be built according to certain general rules, regardless of regional affiliation [3].

CONCLUSION:

So, the task of providing farmers with the necessary information, knowledge and technology should be assigned to information and advisory services. At the same time, the task of the consulting services at the first stage of operation should be the dissemination of modern information technologies, the formation of motivation for the use of scientific achievements, and the provision of advice to farmers based on their current needs. Building a well-functioning information and consulting service will help spread innovative technologies, reduce losses from making wrong decisions, which will allow peasant (farmer) farms to function and develop successfully.

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